
RELIVING PROPHET AMOS' DENUNCIATION OF SOCIAL INJUSTICE AND ITS CHALLENGES TO
THE ACTUALISATION OF VISION 20:2020

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ABSTRACT

The paper examines the challenges of prophet Amos' message in the Nigerian context. It adopts expository and interpretive approaches of the *sitz en leben* in Amos' setting and relates same to the Nigerian scene. The challenges of development facing the nation today are not different from the situations in the time of Amos. The problem of the few rich controlling the wealth of the masses, corruption of judicial procedures, oppression, bribery and idolatry all militated against the socio-economic, security and consequently higher manpower development needs of the nation. The paper discovers among other things that the challenges of security and development facing the nation today, that of brotherly love and care as well as development can only be achieved through a national social reform that is from the heart and not religious fanaticism. It concludes by recommending a turnaround in all sectors of the nation as a tool for the attainment of the national security, love, peace, unity and development.

KEYWORDS: Development, Vision 20:2020, corruption, interpretive, message, challenges.

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INTRODUCTION

The prophet Amos was from Tekoa, a small town about six miles south of Bethlehem and eleven miles from Jerusalem. His name Amos means *burden* or *burden-bearer*. Millard (1985), notes that he earned his living from the flock and the sycamore-fig grove (Amos 1:1; 7:14-15). His call took him from Judah (Southern Kingdom) to Israel (Northern Kingdom). His ministry was during the reigns of Uzziah over Judah (792-740 BC) and Jeroboam II OVER Israel (793-753 BC), hence one can argue that the climax of his ministry falls within 760-750 BC. Amos, a tender of fig tree and shepherd, not a *nabi* but received the message of social reforms for the nations of Judah and Israel at the climax of their prosperity, before they rest on their oasis (Otto, 1965). Hence, the paper seeks to examines the challenges of prophet Amos' message in the Nigerian context amidst oil wealth and extreme poverty of the masses in favour of the bourgeois.

Historical Settings of the Book of Amos

Millard (1985), notes that both kingdoms were enjoying great prosperity and had reached new political and military heights. Consequently, they see it as a time for extravagant indulgence in luxurious living, spreading immorality, corruption of judicial procedures as well as oppressing the poor. Hester (1941) corroborates Millard, adding that despite the nations were threatened by Nineveh, they were enjoying their material prosperity; they allowed themselves to descend into a state of moral corruption and spiritual decay that threatened their very existence.

However, through Amos, God rescued them from disaster. In his condemnation of their wickedness, he outlined the following: immorality, drunkenness, theft, greed, injustice and disregard for the poor, defrauding the helpless, neglect of spiritual duties and forsaking their God. Outwardly, the people were religious, taking pains

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to attend to proper ceremonies, observe the technical regulations and make required offerings; inwardly, they were selfish, cruel, wicked and worldly minded. Going by what Amos declared about himself, it became very clear that it was Yahweh' that led him to sound his trumpet against the nations because of the immoral state.

The message of Amos can be summed up in chapter five of his book, "But let justice roll down like a river, righteousness like a never-failing stream" (5:4). Millard (1985) argues that the verse is a prerequisite for acceptance by God; which the nation of Israel rejected and scorned.

O you who turn justice to wormwood, and cast down righteousness to the earth! They hate him who reproves in the gate, and they abhor him who speaks the truth. Therefore because you trample upon the poor and take from him exactions of wheat, you have built houses of hewn stone, but you shall not dwell in them; you have planted pleasant vineyards, but you shall not drink their wine." (Amos 5:7, 10-11 RSV).

Brown (1999) adds that run down--literally, "roll," that is, to flow abundantly (Isa 48:18). Without the desire to fulfil righteousness in the offerer, the sacrifice is hateful to God (1Sa 15:22; Ps 66:18; Hosea 6:6).

The perversion of justice (verse 7), was the weapon of the wicked in the days of Amos. They corrupted the procedures and institutions of justice (the courts), making them instruments of injustice (bitterness). Laymon (1971) defined the act of perversion of justice as, "wormwood", an exceptionally bitter-tasting plant. The poor, the weak and those who did not have wealth or influence enjoyed no protection from their oppressors; hence the oppressors cast-off restraints (Bitrus, 2006).

Extortions and the pronouncements (verses 10-11). This is based on specific charges of exploitation previously levelled in (verses 6-7); Amos here adds exactions that are extortions in the grain mark and the bribe in the law courts. He therefore warns that the profiteers will never enjoy the security of their houses built of expensive hewn stone.

Challenges of Amos in the Nigerian Context

Nigeria as the giant of Africa is one of the largest geographically about 923,768 km², socially and culturally most diversified African country. It is the most populous country of Africa with her population estimated about 151 million in 2009. The ethnic diversity of the Nigerian society is reflected in the fact that the country has over 250 identified ethnic groups and three main religious groups- African Traditional Religion, Christianity and Islam (World Bank, 2009).

Here, the eight century prophet message is used as a plumb line to evaluate our present situation and the challenge of being numbered among the twenty best economies by the year 2020. This vision seems plausible considering the rich economic situation of the country with abundant human and natural resources yet untapped. It is widely accepted that this economic prosperity is not accompanied by fair distribution of the national wealth; hence some were getting richer from the expanded oil and bilateral trades. The reality of this oligarchy system couched under the guise of democracy is the alarming poverty level being experienced today in the nation; the game of the bourgeois and the proletariats of the Marxist (Isiorhovoja et al, 2011).

Abuchi (2008) while quoting the National Poverty Eradication programme (NEPAD) coordinator Dr. Kparkol, affirms that:

we have over 70 million Nigerians that are poor and we have to watch that poverty rate now very significantly. He said poor people were scattered everywhere in the country, which accounted for the reason why people were so much concerned about the situation...the surest way to overcome inter-generational poverty

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was to have very good education, hence it is important to connect students because they are the leaders of the future.

Relevant questions that can be raised here bothers on the volume of wealth that the Nigerian nation has. Daily, the media are filled with reports of fortunes from black gold, returns from one bad government or personality who has made it to the seat of power or the other under the ambit of the law. Yet, the level of poverty, infrastructural decay and privatisation of government owned companies are on the increase. Kalu (2011) as Nigeria celebrates her 51st independence decried the collapse of Nigeria infrastructure. Among companies that have died he listed the following: Nigeria Airways, Nigeria National Shipping Line, The Volkswgen of Nigeria, Nigerian Cement Industries, ANAMCO, United Kaduna Company and NITEL. Companies on the verge of death include: Peugeot Automobile Nigeria Limited, Daily Times, Nigeria Railway Corporation, Ajaokuta Delta Steel Company, DICON, Nigerian Refineries and Nigerian Paper Mills.

With over fifteen companies dying as a result of our value system, why cry wolf over development when we are not faithful over little. Tosanwumi (2010) blamed the phenomenon on our value system. He argues that our value system, particularly over the last 49 years of self-rule has not provided the needed environment for the proper conduct of government, business and the desired political, social and economic development. These are index of any developing and developed economy to which we aspire by the year and vision 20:2020. Hassan (2008) on his assessment of *National Assembly Members and Self-Representation*, notes that members asked for N114,000.00 (One hundred and fourteen thousand naira) per day per legislature as their lunch. Given the total number of legislature which is 109 multiply by 365, you will discover that we have over N20 billion naira flows freely into their pockets for just a year. A country where avalanche of companies are dying with rising statistics of poverty and corruption level, yet we have a system that will not listen and see hue and cry of the people.

Tosanwumi raised some rhetorical questions: why have they (government) not brought about the development of the country? What is responsible for this deplorable state of affairs? From Hassan's illustration with the National Assembly, we see that among the leadership and the ordinary people, the Nigerian nation is bereft of strong attributes of morality and adherence to fundamental elements of righteousness, honesty and love as exemplified in Luke 9: 51-56; the story of the *Good Samaritan*. Rather, we see callous indifference. The underprivileged, physically challenged, aged, youths and poverty ridden persons in our midst treated as outcasts. Nwaebuni(2004) lamented the *Many Faces of Materialism* similar to the ones in Amos context for the nations to rise up from the slumber of death and socio-economic cum religious profanity that is abominable to God. The call in our present day has come from the ambassador of rebranding, Prof. Dora Akinyuli but the scene has not yet changed because the heart has not got the message hence, and there are cases of electoral riggings, post-election violence and the incessant gate crashing of offended flag-bearers with petitions against their opponents over instances of electoral fraud. The appalling situation in most of the filed petitions is that the judges are corrupt; they cannot deliver the right judgment because of bribe. God's intervention in the lives of the people requires the free flow of justice but not until the situation is truly sanitised, there is not going to be justice and the monster hydra called corruption will continue to prevail rearing its ugly head.

Vision 20:2020 Myth or Reality

The hue and cry of the Nigerian populace is to experience meaningful development that will lead to the total emancipation of the people from the shackles of poverty and hunger amidst plenty as a result of the Marxist political economy with features of oligarchy to undo the people. From pre-colonial era, the message of the prophet has resonated as the panacea to meaningful human capital and equitable distribution of wealth as enshrined in the Willink's Commission as in the case of the Niger Delta and the nation's experience of denied opportunities, from the imperial overlords, through military dictatorship and loss of scholars in the like of Ken Saro-Wiwa to the present day manipulated self-representation under the tunic of democracy.

Bonaventure Suwai definition of development as quoted by Mato (2009) is *the direct opposite of underdevelopment*. He notes the twin complex phenomena have since remained central and occupied primacy in

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the unending search for solutions to the endemic catastrophes that are facing the majority of our peoples on the continent of Africa in general and Nigeria in particular. Dr. Otive Igbuzor in his work, "Challenges of Development in Nigeria" argues that:

Nigeria fares poorly in all development indices. This is because the country's performance at development has remained abysmally poor as it has persistently been ranked amongst the poorest human settlements even with abundant mineral and human resources. Nigeria could best be described as a country potentially too rich to be poor. Yet poverty and underdevelopment remains the reality of the Nigerian situations.

To say that Nigeria is stagnant sometimes may imply that the nation is not moving forward but the same class of persons have steered the affairs of this nation to their personal gains. At the 50th independence celebration, a one-time vice president, woke up from his slumber and exclaimed: "its time for reflection", an open confession in attestation to the wide gap between the rich and the poor; between our potentials and our achievements. We have no reason to be poor given the rich endowments of this nation. Were these revelations nascent to him after his tenure in office or they are intuitions that came to him after some sweet moments of brainstorming on what Nigeria ought to be? (Ezea, 2010). Igbuzor contends that as a nation, we need development. Thank God for the different strategies – The Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) with its laudable objectives aiming at 2015, a time to eradicate poverty, gender discrimination, health (maternal and child) amongst others. But these policies do not translate into programmes on their own, there has to be manifestation of this development that will lead to increased capacity of the peoples to have control over material assets, intellectual resources and ideology; to obtain physical necessities of life like food, clothing and shelter. Employment, equal participation without oppression in the government and society, adequate education, gender equality, sustainable development and peace are sine qua non.

Umoh and Essien (2011), carefully examined the gender issues in Nigeria in the just concluded election and came out with astonishing result of the sharp margins that exist. For the National Assembly, result, only six women out of eighty-six seats while that of the Federal House of Representatives, we have only three women out of eighty-nine seats. These figures do not represent progress as argued Igbuzor on his evaluation of the nation's journey so far. Some reasons which could be termed trivial are responsible for this occurrence in the annals of the nation. It is better imagined than experienced the volume of feminine potentials that Nigeria is wasting as a result of women non-inclusion in policies and programmes implementation annually. While third world countries of Asia are fully harnessing female potentials, Nigeria the giant of Africa is foot-dragging to implement such policies of women inclusion in her plans.

The presence of good government that is ready to empower the people will make the laudable vision 20:2020 feasible; however, the government of the day has not proved to the masses their capability. Amos in his charge to the nations of Israel and Judah demanded justice like a stream. The few elites who manage the affairs of the nation for self-aggrandisement show that the state is not just deceiving the subordinate class but the ruling class such that the act of deception has been elevated to national norm (Mato, 2009).

The failure of the judiciary in Nigerian system has contributed to the decadence of the society as it is widely acclaimed that justice delayed is justice denied. The acting Chief Judge of Nigeria (CJN), Justice Dahiru Mustapha at the opening of the special session of the Supreme Court conceded to the corrupt practices levelled against lawyers in the courts and promised to bring sanity (Ehiabhi, 2011). Prophet Joel said, "...and rend your hearts and not your garments." Return to the LORD, your God, for he is gracious and merciful, slow to anger, and abounding in steadfast love, and repents of evil" (RSV). Adams (2009) notes that the verse above has a greater implication for the civil society; he adds that in rending the heart, let it not be merely a rending of your garments, but let your hearts be truly contrite. Merely external worship and hypocritical pretensions will only increase the evil, and cause God to meet out heavier judgments. The selective attitude of the government in

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protecting sacred cows while others are slaughtered further proved the ingenuity of the Yar' Adua-Jonathan's anticorruption credentials. The Obasanjo's administration is not void of similar account as there were some of the most devious schemes ever derived in the history of Nigeria, all calculated to fleece the Nigerian people, but almost always packaged with pretence at some altruistic purposes for the national good.

The altruistic attitude has made the leaders to quickly abandon certain noble steps and strides of the past. In the National Anthem, we sing, "Arise O compatriot Nigeria's call obey, to serve our father's land with love and strength and faith..." However, the scene has not witnessed the presence of the compatriot that will serve with obedience, love and faithfulness for the sake of the fatherland. The different regimes and administrations have raised the hope of the people with laudable programmes as anticipate the vision 20:2020 only to hoodwink them in the near future as attempts at fooling the people by failing and deceitful governing few.

Igbuzor contends that some of the reasons responsible for their failure and stagnation of the nation's growth strategies include: inadequate funding of the educational system which will produce the needed human capital for the much talked about national development; the challenge of attaining the millennium development goals, the challenge of HIV/AIDS, corruption, budgeting, civil society participation in governance, trade unionism and the challenge of democratisation. The bane of Nigeria problem therefore, is not in the policy formulation rather it lies in the implementation. Vision 20:2020 though its quite a number of years from now its success lies on the "compatriot" that will stand to implement the programme. This has been the problem which Dr. Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala diagnosed of the nation's perennial problem of underdevelopment.

CONCLUSION

The paper examined the background of Prophet Amos and the live situations of the nations of Israel and Judah. Their experiences were contextualised based on the present scenario of Nigeria. It was discovered among other things that both nations of Judah, Israel and Nigeria shared so much in common. Their leaders were corrupt because of the nation's wealth which they have treasured up for themselves. They made the judicial system subservient to themselves as a tool for perpetuating their dastard acts against the poor.

To this end, there were serious socio-economic problems that plague the country as the poor masses become even more faceless and voiceless because of the level of poverty that stares at them. Hence, there were many teething problems that clog the wheel of progress of the nation. Other vital organs that deserved attention were played down upon because it will not yield the bourgeois dividends such as investment in public sector and other development projects aimed at the masses. Because of these, many policies and programme were never executed in the nation, the reason being that there is no justice, equity and fair-play in Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Vision 20:2020 is a laudable programme but first, let there be a social reform in the system, such that will come from the heart as Amos declared before the nations.
- Moral awakening should be embarked upon, the dearth of worthy men in the nation's political scene as well as the judiciary, speaks more that volumes about the level of our preparedness for the attainment of any noble objective such as Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and vision 20:2020
- The vast natural and human resources of the nation should be made to reflect on the daily lives of the people as well as empowering them through effective participation in policies, programmes and implementation.
- There have been series of development planning in Nigeria; the government should focus on effective implementation strategies with checks and balances that can help to rejuvenate the people and the society in general.
- More people oriented projects should be executed to raise the poverty level. We cannot think global when we have thought of the locality in which we live.
- Gender, education, employment among others should be prioritised by the government to raise the level of manpower needs of the state.

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